

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF VENTRICULAR TACHYARRHYTHMIAS IN
MODERN INTERPRETATION

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Abstract. *This thesis presents information about the clinical manifestations of ventricular tachyarrhythmias in a modern interpretation.*

keywords: *ventricular tachyarrhythmias, asymptomatic cases, Palpitations, extrasystole, dizziness.*

КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ЖЕЛУДОЧКОВЫХ ТАХИАРИТМИЙ В
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ.

Аннотация. *В диссертации представлены сведения о клинических проявлениях желудочковых тахикардий в современной интерпретации.*

Ключевые слова: *желудочковые тахикардии, бессимптомные случаи, сердцебиение, экстрасистолия, головокружение.*

Relevance of the problem: Clinical manifestations of ventricular tachyarrhythmias can vary significantly - from absolutely asymptomatic cases to palpitations, chest discomfort, chest pain, suffocation, dizziness, presyncope and fainting, and blood until complete cessation of circulation. Palpitations, dizziness, and syncope are the three most important symptoms that require a careful history and further investigation to rule out VT. With ventricular extrasystole, the patient usually complains of cardiac arrest, interruptions in its work, tremors and tremors in the area of the heart. In an atypical location, chest pain, weakness, and dizziness may occur. In addition, heart rhythm disturbances can cause anxiety, fear of death and, in more severe cases, panic in the patient. Complaints about interruptions in heart activity during extrasystole may be related to provoking factors (smoking, alcohol, excessive physical activity, etc.) and / or exacerbation of the disease that causes extrasystole. However, symptoms of arrhythmia may appear without any triggering factors.

Research materials: The diagnosis of ventricular extrasystole is confirmed on the basis of objective examination, cardiac auscultation data, electrocardiography (ECG) and 24-hour Holter ECG monitoring.

Object of the study: During the objective examination, attention is paid to the clear pulsation of the jugular veins, which occurs when the ventricles contract prematurely. A characteristic feature is an uneven pulse with a long pause after an emergency contraction of the heart.

During auscultation, arrhythmic sounds of the heart, a change in the tone of the first tone (caused by the sound of the closing of the mitral and tricuspid valves and appears during the contraction of the ventricle), and a split of the second tone (appears in a short time) can be heard. the time during which the heart relaxes due to occlusion of the aorta and pulmonary arteries).

Observational results of the study: the diagnosis of ventricular extrasystole can be confirmed only by means of instrumental studies. If there is a suspicion of ventricular extrasystole, the patient first undergoes an ECG examination, which allows recording the emergency QRS complex. A standard 12-lead ECG can help identify genetic disorders associated with ventricular arrhythmia (VA) and sudden cardiac death (SCD), such as channelopathies (long QT syndrome and short QT syndrome, Brugada syndrome, CPVT) and cardiomyopathies (ARC and). HCM). Structural heart pathology is indicated by ECG signs such as His bundle block, atrioventricular (AV) block, ventricular hypertrophy, and Q wave characteristic of coronary heart disease or infiltrative cardiomyopathy.

The use of echocardiography to assess LV and RV function and detect structural cardiac pathology is recommended for all patients with suspected or confirmed VT or at high risk of developing severe VA or SCD.

Conclusions: If ventricular arrhythmias are known or suspected to be induced by physical activity, it is recommended that patients undergo dosed physical activity testing for diagnosis, to determine prognosis, and to evaluate the results of drug therapy or RFA.

Exercise stress testing (electrocardiography/echocardiography/perfusion single-photon emission computed tomography) in VA patients with a moderate or high probability of SA based on age or symptoms to induce ischemic changes or ventricular arrhythmia) is recommended. as well as to clarify the diagnosis and prognosis in cases of exercise-induced VT or suspicion of this pathology, including catecholaminergic polymorphic VT.

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